

The Oklo Phenomenon

Robert Wechsler

The Oklo Phenomenon is a solo dance piece controlling sound and light with movement. The performer(s) uses eye movement, facial gesture and body movement to control stage lighting and sound. The synergistic effect of all three of these media — movement, light and sound — generates a unique relationship between the performer and his surroundings as they become both an outside force with which he is confronted and a reflection of his own psyche.